

Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) Maintenance of Children's Well-Being at the Orphanage

Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari

St. Xavier's College, Maitighar, Kathmandu, Nepal

ORDT: Organization for Research Development and Training Pvt. Ltd. Lalitpur, Nepal
info@ordt.com.np
manirajbhandari@sxc.edu.np

Abstract: *Well-being is essential for everyone, and it is even more necessary for children, especially those who are sheltering in an orphanage. The well-being of children can be integrated with many essential factors, their Psychological growth, Social environment, and physiological development. This requires maintenance in Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters. The purpose of this study is to explore the adequacy of the well-being of abandoned and orphan children being fostered at the orphanage. A qualitative methodology was applied. A narrative analysis was interpreted to explore the subjective meaning of the children's adequacy to psychological, social, and physiological parameters. Altogether, twelve respondents participated, two were social workers, and ten were children. The interview was scheduled for 40 to 60 minutes. Triangulation analysis was applied and gave meaning through the crystallisation method. Findings suggest that a desirable social environment can enhance and enrich the holistic development of the child, enabling children's growth and development in multiple ways. Sociological parameters enhance a child to learn and act, developing the cognition of a child as a socially accepted individual. Physiological parameters maintenance can also have a sensitivity and responsiveness effect on shaping the disciplines through educative means and physical activities. This enhances the sensitivity and responsiveness amongst and between children through cognitive development and enriches their social behaviour. Psychological parameters are strong and can have multiple reciprocal changes in all Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters, including on their own psychological platform. Psychological parameters are far more multi-dimensional and can have their own reciprocity effects on their own dimension, both positively and negatively. Maintenance Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters are tightly intertwined with each other and are inseparable, and may not be significantly applicable at the same time. Single-parameter maintenance can equally offer a significant contribution to the well-being of all, to enhance the growth and development of individuals and groups. Maintenance of these parameters can be focused on a single parameter to enhance the other two parameters. The mirror effect of one single parameter can have a simultaneous and spontaneous reciprocity effect on the maintenance of the other parameters.*

Keywords: Psychological; sociological; physiological; mirror effect; reciprocity effect; sensitivity; responsiveness; orphans; well-being

Introduction

Children are considered the future of the nation. The formation of human capital of the nation entirely depends on the upbringing of an individual since childhood (Schoellman, 2016; Saracoğlu & Karaoğlu, 2016). Moreover, in a developing country like Nepal, where the need for human capital is felt to be necessary, a deep thought towards developing a powerful citizen for the future is also necessary. However, most children are still abandoned on the street (UNICEF, 2024; Gahungu, Simbananiye, and Glowacz, 2024; Correvon, 2010). Few social organizations have lent their hand to foster these children by providing shelter, clothing, and food, which are considered a basic need of human beings, fulfilling the well-being journey of the stranded child.

The modern world, integrated with Artificial Intelligence (AI), requires sharp, intelligent-minded people. This is because it is also integrated into organisational lives to support the Human Intelligence Minds (HIM) (Rajbhandari, 2025). An intelligent mind can be fostered by bringing up a child with adequate needs-based facilities from childhood. However, their well-being is considered the most essential factor for their brain to develop. The well-being of children can be integrated with many essential factors, their Psychological growth, Social environment, and their Physiological development. This requires a maintenance in Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) (Rajbhandari, 2015a, 2015b, 2016). These three essential factors maintain the children's well-being.

Moreover, adequate well-being of a child at an early age can define their healthy development, which is a complex process (OECD, 2020; Lewis, 2019; Child Trends, 2016), but at a later stage, a child can thus contribute and significantly become a human capital for their nation (Social Protection Civil Society Network et al., 2023; UNICEF 2015). Considering this, not many organisations are fostering children within their care. Nevertheless, few organisations in Nepal are prioritising their willingness to care for the children who are abandoned and orphans (Gale and Khatiwada 2016). It is believed that the organisations that care for these orphans are highly motivated to foster any kind of child who has been abandoned and has become an orphan. Within these kinds of children, diversified groups of children are constantly being fostered in an orphanage. These diversified groups include all kinds of children with special abilities of all kinds. Moreover, all kinds of diversified children are equally grouped into one category as orphans. Special care for special children is provided; however, proper care for these special kinds can vary from mental, physical, and emotional.

Orphanage care is segmented into different types based on gender. While studying the orphanage care for the orphans and abandoned children of diversified groups, an orphanage offers shelters to foster children by providing the needy care for the children, such as food, clothes, and shelter. In addition, these children are also provided with basic education at the orphanage by trained staff.

It is difficult to predict the children's development in the later part of their lives, although the orphanage has been operating its social contributions for a long time. However, at the early

stage of fostering children, their growth and development are completely dependent upon the care provided by the orphanage.

The development of children is segmented into various elements, Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters (Rajbhandari 2015a, 2015b, 2016). These Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters can be related to basic needs of every human being, such as food, clothing, and shelter, which provide a social environment, physiological development, and psychological stability, thus offering well-being at all levels. However, the adequacy of these basic need factors can have a positive and negative correlation with the PSP parameter, leading to development and contribution as human capital to the nation.

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to explore the adequacy of the well-being of abandoned and orphan children being fostered at the orphanage. This study was conducted to disseminate information and knowledge about the orphans being fostered at the orphanage. This study was conducted with the following research questions,

1. How are the orphans and abandoned children fostered in the social environment at the orphanage?
2. How are their psychological and physiological development being fostered at the orphanage?

Methodology and methods

The applied methodology for this study was a qualitative design. A narrative analysis was interpreted to explore the subjective meaning of the children's adequacy to Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters. However, adequacy is a relative term and is subjective. For this study, adequacy was qualitatively judged by assessing the adequacy of basic needs for the fostered children PSP within the orphanage.

Research method

An interview schedule was developed to explore the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters relating to the adequacy of basic needs (food, clothing, and shelter) instigating well-being. Thirteen children and two social-work staff from the orphanage were interviewed. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with the children and social workers from the orphanage. Notes were also taken during the interview, and the interview was scheduled for 40 to 60 minutes. During the interview with the thirteen children, sensitive and emotional questions were skipped and discarded. Mature children were randomly selected who were able to understand the questions and their meaning. The questions were asked in the local language and were translated into English. All interviews were taken at the same time with different children. The translated version of the interview data was analysed by applying the data triangulation method (Denzin, 1970) for reliability and validation (Carmines and Zeller, 1979), and the crystallisation method (Ellingson, 2008) was further applied to give credible meaning to the raw data.

Theoretical construction

Figure 1 Theoretical construction on the theoretical discourse Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters (Rajbhandari, 2015a, 2015b, 2016)

The theoretical construction is based on the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) discourse on leadership maintenance, where a mirror effect can cause a reciprocity effect on the followers, given the contextual settings (Rajbhandari, 2015a, 2015b, 2016). PSP is generated by the organisational leader through the organisational context to develop strategic fit for the followers. In the context of an orphanage, a contextual setting (the climatic/cultural environment) and the followers (children/staff) are led by the vision of the organisational leader (Chairperson). A specific Immediate Contextual Variation can both agitate and shape the organisational culture (Rajbhandari, 2013). A good culture shapes the desired PSP parameters; however, in the case of an orphanage, a good culture and climate are essential to shape the adequacy of PSP parameters, which play a vital role in shaping the mindfulness psycho-socio-physio (PSP) parameters of children. In this theoretical construction, an extension of PSP is applied to generate further understanding beyond a social well-being maintenance of the foster ship and fostering of orphans or abandoned children. These children are completely dependent on the organisational strategies groomed with adequacy of basic needs, including education and training, which further enables the sheltered children to maintain their adequacy of required Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) in the future and present.

Findings and discussion

A narrative interpretive analysis was conducted to provide meaning to the primary data. The narration of the story was dictated by the children at the orphanage who were brought for shelter and provided with necessities and basic needs. The narrated data was interpreted to give meaning to the raw data further.

The findings and discussions are aligned with the theoretical discourse Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters developed by Rajbhandari in 2015a, 2015b, 2016. The Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters discuss the maintenance of sociological, psychological and physiological parameters amongst the children sheltered in the orphanage. The sociological parameters interpret the social environments supporting the fostering of children's growth, and the psychological and physiological parameters discuss the overall mindfulness development of the children living away from their families within the contextual settings. Although this study takes the inclination on the subjective discourse, the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) maintenance has a generalizability instance of the children's growth and development while living with diverse groups of children and with different ages, backgrounds and abilities.

Psychological, Sociological, and Physiological maintenance parameters for well-being **Sociological parameters for well-being**

Within Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters, sociological maintenance is highly essential, especially for the children who are isolated due to being abandoned by their family for being different due to their special abilities and various causes such as economy, marital issues, etc. Sociological maintenance enhances the growth of individuals through different means, such as social learning and cognitive development (Bandura, 1999). Regarding the causes of the separation of the child, there could be many aspects related to a few of the causes are mentioned by the respondent, Social workers (SW1), for which she entails;

A variety of causes of abandonment issues are found, a few of them are poverty, uneducated parents, family issues, abuse, both online & physical, but educating the abandoned child will provide social awareness, and even men are abused, and the child has rights to education and to be in a social environment.

A desirable social environment can enhance and enrich the holistic development of the child. While this is not focused elsewhere, living in a shelter with many other similar-aged groups, a recognised shelter can provide a daily social routine task for all. This enables the children's growth and development in multiple ways, physiologically, socially, and psychologically. This supports the respondent SW2, says;

They get up, then freshen up, tidy their bed, do their daily routine, have their breakfast, clean their house, do taekwondo on Sunday, Wednesday, do exercise, dance class on Wednesday, Thursday, have their breakfast and then play games, have assembly, then start to read after studying, they draw and do fun activities and have lunch. After lunch, they play outdoor games. After games, they have a sharing session along with watching T.V. In night till 9:00, they play after having dinner and go to bed.

Following up on the same social parameters with the children, all accept the social environment at the shelter and the procedures, which offered a disciplined atmosphere for further development. In the same vein, R5 mentions supporting this view, stating

Wake up in the morning, freshen up, clean the space, do breakfast, do exercise and then play and have lunch. Then go to study. Have lunch around 2 P.M and then go to play and watch T.V. Then they have a sharing session about what they did the whole day. Then they have dinner and play indoor games. Then they study, do their homework, and sleep.

Sociological parameters are essential for all, and it is even more necessary for a growing child to learn and act while also socially learning. This further develops the cognition of a child for better understanding the perspective of life and for creating socially accepted individuals in a society and community. This view can be supported by the response made by respondents R2 and R3 for which they states;

Respondent R2

With the help of teachers, this institute provides me with everything. With the help of teachers and the organisation, we are provided with food and everything, it is fully satisfied for us. I enjoyed being in this place. It's so fun to be here.

Respondent R3

By living together, we learn to do homework. It's exciting to be there. All of them are good and friendly. They treat us with good behaviour, polite words and all. They are friendly to me. They are helpful and kind enough.

Sociological parameters are engraved with both actions and reactions (Albarracín, Dai, and White, 2019), with their own approaches and those of others. It is interlinked with the psychological aspect to develop a positive state of mind within oneself and others, and further generates physiological parameters for growth with others through building group dynamism and becoming resourceful while remaining within a similar group.

Physiological parameters for well-being

Physiological parameters have two sides: the external source and the internal source. The external source is the outsourced funding that keeps the sound infrastructure for the shelter, and the one who experiences it while at the shelter. The internal source is the execution of the physiological resources that are benefited by the sheltered children while they are living at the shelter. Moreover, the physiological parameters are measured by how the growth of children is simultaneously taken care of while providing the available entertaining resources that have been offered by the external partner organisations that have come to use for the sheltered children. The physiological parameters are the major source of maintaining the well-being of children during their stay at their maturity stage. The external physiological parameters in the orphanage are maintained by external sources for physical activities and educational purposes. The maintenance of physiological parameters can only be possible with the support that has been rendered by the external agencies for the sake of improving the sheltered children. Similarly, this orphanage shelter home is also supported by the external agencies and the government, as the respondent SW1 mentions;

Education & Health provision are supported by the funds provided by the government. Other agencies from university from United Kingdom fund the organisation and also send their students for an internship. While the majority of the funds are allocated to the government, to which we rely the most.

The funds that are allocated by external sources are maintained for infrastructural development, including the physical facilities for the children to enjoy and entertain, for the healthy growth and encouraging them to further develop their skills through playing, exercises and team building approaches.

Moreover, physiological parameters that measure the direct impact on the children's growth and development can also be related to games and playing activities that are available for the children. These facilities are of direct concern for the children to interact and team building socially and develop psychological skills. This is supported by the responses that are given by the orphanage children respondents while they were asked about the physiological parameters development in the orphanage organisation, which are basically designed as a plan and program for the sheltered children. The orphanage children respondent R8 mentions by saying;

Respondent R8

He likes to play football, badminton, carom board, table tennis, and cricket. He exercises & does yoga in the morning. He interacts with his friends and has friendly behaviour.

Supporting this view, respondents R1 and R10 also add by saying

Respondent R1

We have fun, we get to study, play games, and we take this place as a way to get an education and move forward. A safe place for us.

Physiological parameters maintenance can also have a sensitivity and responsiveness effect on shaping the disciplines of the children. This is supported by the response made by the respondent 10 for which he says;

We brush teeth, manage bed, do yoga and meditation. There is a time for lunch, games, studying time, and watching T.V at the leisure time. We are being frequently visited by different students from various colleges as they come for their internship. We have lively activities and are not only focused on education alone. We grow up to become different individuals from the skill-gaining training we receive, and independent funders and family support the organisation for the sake of our development. Sometimes the family also accept the sheltered child after they have grown up in the shelter. There is also government support, and there are more cases where parents take their child back home with them after growing up in this organisation.

Sensitivity and responsiveness effects can have multiple parameters for the measurement of growth and development in a child. These multiple measuring parameters are visible through physical growth and cognitive development. Within cognitive development parameters, education can be one of the major indicators for improvement. Moreover, an orphanage shelter home has designed their educative planning through different modalities. One of the educational modalities is teaching, learning and examination preparation until matriculation. In connection with this, respondent SW2 states;

All orphan children study in this organisation. We have a classroom for students of different ages and grades. They study in this organization but for exams, we prepare them and send them to take their test/exams in a different school, with which we have collaborated. We have also arranged for intern teachers to teach our children, which is good for the children to learn from educated people.

Through assimilations of both educative means and physical activities, children can benefit and acquire a sense of social belongingness. This enhances the sensitivity and responsiveness amongst and between children through cognitive development and enriches their social behaviour. This is supported by the responses from the orphan children from the orphanage shelter, which reflect their views regarding their cognitive approaches and social behaviours with themselves and others.

Respondents R1

We learn by studying, exercising, basic routine, and we enjoy having fun and playing taekwondo. There are many things we don't know, and every day something new is happening here. We do enjoy staying at this place.

Respondent R2

We spend our time playing and running. We play with our friends, and we do homework with the help of teachers. It's fun, good and exciting about this place. It's very good, hope it will also get much better, and there should be more people around here. All children are friendly and are good and best for us

Respondent R3

I enjoyed this place. I play football and other sports.

Respondent R4

We spend our day meditating, studying, and playing games after 2 pm (football, carom, basketball). Playing, studying, and talking with their friends

Respondent R6

We are enjoying ourselves here. We do lots of activities such as Singing, dancing, playing taekwondo, football, badminton, table tennis, carom board, volleyball, chess, Ludo, and cube. We have both indoor/outdoor games

Respondent R7

We enjoy playing, watching T.V, dancing, physical exercises and studying. It is fun and enjoyable. We are given a chance if anyone makes mistakes, but after the chances are over, they will get punishment.

Respondent R9

We wake up at 6, and start cleaning up at 7, then we have tea, and at 8 to 9 we do our yoga/exercise, 9 to 10 we play games, we have our lunch at 10, and from 11 to-2 we have our class when we study. Snack time is at 2, after that we play outdoor games until 5 pm. Our sharing session begins at 5, while dinner is served at 7, between 8 and 9 we watch T.V and finally we all go to sleep. Besides these schedules, we also share our feelings with all. Some are friendly, and some are introverted. But we treat each other with love and respect. We enjoy playing with each other. Sometimes we might be tight, but at the end of the day, we solve their problem. If somebody is sad, we console them.

Physiological parameters maintenance can have multiple effects on the growth and development of a child. Although PSP parameters are likely intertwined with each other, they are not mutually exclusive. This can have the sensitivity and responsiveness effect as of the mirror effect, producing the reciprocity reflection through the lens of each PSP parameter. Although all the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters maintenance is essential, high maintenance of any PSP parameters can be defined by the contextual settings of the organisation. In connection to this, maintenance of physiological parameters in the Nepalese organisational contextual setting is determined by the need for upgrades in physical infrastructural development, which thus can enhance and enrich the growth of children through both cognitive and social learning activities.

Psychological parameter for well-being

Within the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters, the psychological parameter is essential. Although psychological parameters are invisible, but it can contribute to the wholesome growth and development of individuals and groups differently, thus enriching the cognitive and social approaches. PSP parameters are multi-dimensional but not mutually exclusive, and can be enhanced to reflect a higher possibility of mental, physical, cognitive, and social growth for holistic development in individuals and groups, generating a mirror effect to reflect the reciprocity image from oneself as well as to and from others. Consequently, within PSP parameters, psychological parameters can therefore have a separate maintenance for the well-being of a child and their group within an organisation.

While sensitivity can have a responsiveness effect, psychological parameters maintenance can generate a mirror effect by bringing about changes through a single dimension. Within Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters, psychological parameter maintenance is also essential to address with utmost importance due to the nature of its mirror effect towards reflecting reciprocal changes in social and physiological growth and development in individuals.

Psychological parameters are strong and can have multiple reciprocal changes in all Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters, including on their own psychological platform. Thus, maintenance of psychological parameters can have a reciprocal effect on psychological, social and physiological development and growth, consequently, generating a mirror effect on the psychology of an individual also. Therefore, psychological parameters are far more multi-dimensional and can have their own reciprocity effects on their own dimension, both positively and negatively.

Within the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP), psychological parameter is maintained to develop the individual's state of mind by creating an environment that fits to all children living in the same organisation. This generates a self-awareness within individuals in making a self-decisive action on their own, thus generating a reciprocal reflection through the mirror effect of psychological enrichment towards bringing about changes in sociological and physiological parameters. This supports the answers given by the respondents below. Respondent SW 1, a social worker in the orphanage, explains

It is a Self-choice of being here, and it's their right, in terms of getting shelter and education. We ask them first with all sorts of questions, such as why they would want to stay, what their interests are and where they would want to belong in this organisation. We include everyone equally, and there is no one is left alone. Different children have different choices of actions; some would prefer education and some skilful activities, such as talent demonstration (singing and dancing), skill shows, and some are introverted and demonstrate their works in different ways. Overall, we display a wall magazine so that it is visible to all and which eventually motivates others to participate.

She further adds by saying;

Abandoned children are brought here by the police, child missing centres, and we seek their official permission first to admit the child here. Sometime parent leave their child of their own will, and we do have parental counselling for this. We ask the parents to visit their child/children for three months on a timely basis. Initially, there is always a behavioural issue with the child, and they lack the knowledge of abandonment by their parents. There could be various reasons for parent to abandon their child. We have both individual and group counselling, which will help them to accept staying here.

Respondent SW 2, another social worker, states,

The reason for abandonment could be various reasons. Although most are coming here from sober families, and some children are left to stay in different organisations like ours, and in some cases, children are found abandoned, such as runaway cases. Nepalese police find them and bring them to us. The reason for runaway cases is increasing, this is due to the fact that in that organisation, people used to hit them in the name of improving them. There is even a case where another organisation did not care whether or not they died and hit on their head if the children had anything to say

against. If any mistake was made, they would repeatedly get beating from the organisation members.

A psychological state of mind develops when an individual realises the conducive environment that they are living in. This enhances their social relational behaviour and physiological growth, instigating psychological development of belongingness. Within the Psycho-socio-physio (PSP) parameters, maintaining psychological parameter have intertwined elements that associate social and physiological factors. Psychological parameters are positively interconnected with social relational behaviour with others and in groups, while the physiological factors are connected with team building, team bonding and team banking amongst and between the individuals and groups.

Respondents' answers towards how psychological development enhances both their social being and physiological growth by mentioning

Respondent R1

Caretakers are very friendly here. They give their whole attention to the children. Children are friendly and cooperative as well. Everyone in this organization treat each other well and is supportive of each other.

Respondent R2

My friend treats me very well. My friend teaches me the moral lessons and tells me to focus more on my studies and become a successful person.

Respondent R3

My friends are very kind and helpful. Sometimes we fight, but still we forgive each other very quickly. They are friendly enough

Respondent R4

Caretakers here are very good in nature, and sometimes guardians/parents also visit their child; children can also call their parents.

Respondent R5

The caretakers of this organisation are friendly. They treat each other like brothers, sometimes they also argue, but after a few times they become good friends. We take care of ourselves, and we become sick, then the staff care about us

Respondent R8

We enjoy staying in this place. The staff are friendly and treat us well. They discuss their feelings, thoughts and behaviour with each other. They treat us with love and care. They sometimes scold us if we don't behave well. Some are friendly, and some children are introverted. But we treat each other with love and respect. We enjoy playing with each other. Sometimes we might argue, but at the end of the day, we solve our problem. If somebody is sad, we console them.

Respondent R9

This is a Beautiful place, and we have fun and joy together. We are provided with delicious food to eat. Even though we borrow and lend our belonging for example, when someone doesn't have a pencil, some of us will let him borrow ours.

Respondent R10

This is a beautiful place to stay with always-evergreen surroundings, and we are provided with education and proper hygiene. We are being treated well here. We help each other like our own brothers. And sometimes we tease each other by making funny comments, which will end up in a big laugh. Everyone is enjoying the time here.

Development of the psychological state of mind, which offers well-being, is also integrated with social and physiological parameters. Children sheltering at the orphanage associate their behaviours with social relationships and physiological adequacy. Psychological parameters can enrich the children's well-being, which consciously and subconsciously associate their development through the sociological and physiological enhancement. Thus, psychological parameters maintenance simultaneously assimilates the sociological and physiological parameters maintenance and generates a holistic development and growth in a child.

Discussion

Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters for maintenance of well-being are essential for all. These parameters are both equipped with intrinsic and extrinsic growth that leads to the development of mind, health and soundness of individuals. The Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters are the reflection and generate a mirror effect, causing a reciprocity effect through learning by Divergence (feeling/watching), Assimilating (watching/thinking), converging (doing/thinking) and Accommodating (doing/feeling) (Kolb, 1981). The mirror effect is replicated and learned to generate experiential learning, further to making a critical decision-making and thinking process. A mirror effect generates a reciprocity learning behaviour by divergence, assimilation, conversion, and accommodation.

Not all these Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters are mutually exclusive; they are mutually unexclusive, and thus single parameters are prone to cause a mirror effect of the learning behaviour through both social and cognitive. A reciprocity effect caused by the mirror reflection is transitioning parameters, which are learned through the replication behaviour of others; this, therefore, generates a feeling, watching, thinking and doing behaviour in individuals. While these behaviours are engraved into a Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters, an individual can release each type of learned behaviour through a single mirror reflection or by combining all these parameters. The mirror effect, which causes the reciprocity image, can have both negative and positive consequences. Nevertheless, in these cases, a learned behaviour is constrained to one or multiple learning paradigms through feeling, watching, thinking and doing. Moreover, one or more of these learning paradigms may or may not be deeply ingrained in the understanding of the individuals. However, with the reciprocity effect, of replication of the mirror effect, the feeling, watching, thinking and doing may not be

the same with all individuals, generating a different reciprocity effect with the same mirror effect.

Figure 2. Well-being through the mirror effect of Sociological parameters maintenance

Figure 2 illustrates the mirror effect of sociological parameters producing a reciprocity effect on psychological and physiological parameters, thereby regenerating well-being (state of mind) through building relational approaches (socialising) with various activities, including both educative and physical curricula.

Although Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) are intertwined with each other, it is also found that a change in a single parameter can have an equal and opposite effect on the other parameters. However, changes in all these Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) at the same time may not be feasible, and it is also recommended to bring about systematic changes on one single parameter that will further instigate the positive effect on the other two parameters.

Moreover, a mirror effect of a single parameter, for example, psychological parameters, can be reflected in a one-dimensional psychological reciprocity; however, a multiple mirror effect of all Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters can have a multi-dimensional reflection, which is difficult to generate a replicable reciprocity effect. This is due to the differences in cognitive learning and social learning behaviours. Nevertheless, these Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters are necessary for all for the maintenance of well-being, furthering to developing their wholesomeness as individuals that enables them to fit in the groups and the environmental settings.

Figure 3. Well-being through the mirror effect of Psychological parameters maintenance

Figure 3 illustrates the mirror effect of the psychological parameter on the sociological and physiological parameters. Psychological parameters are deeply engraved, and is tightly intertwined with the other two parameters. Moreover, psychological parameters are invisible due to its high sensitivity to emotions, perceptions, values, learning, etc. and can have a direct correlation with the other parameters. A systematic change brought about in psychological parameters can have positive responsiveness and a systematic reciprocity effect on other parameters (sociological and physiological), including its own parameter (psychological).

Although Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) is studied in single parameters, the variations in the degree of each parameter can occur. The variation can be in any of these Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters and in the individual's learning paradigm. Any of these variation either in PSP or in the individuals, can cause a mirror effect towards different reciprocity effects. However, Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters cannot be ignored or avoided. These Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters need maintenance on a recurring basis, this is due to the change in environment, changes that affect individuals and variations in the contextual settings. The maintenance of PSP is required to be refurbished to replenish the internal growth to strategically fit in with the external changes and development. Nevertheless, not all these Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) maintenance may require simultaneous refurbishment, thus maintenance of a single parameter can replenish a well-maintained behaviour seeking the well-being of oneself and others in the group. However, with the demand of contextual settings, maintenance of any Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters may require additional attention than other Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP); a learning understanding attitude to refurbish any PSP is utmost important. This is because refurbishing one PSP for maintenance can generate a mirror effect in multiple reflections, and if the maintenance of unessential Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters is refurbished, it can thus reflect multiple rays of the same kind and can produce a different reciprocity effect.

Figure 4. Well-being through the mirror effect of Physiological parameters maintenance

Figure 4 illustrates that physiological parameters support sociological and psychological parameters in an independent manner. Although physiological parameters tend to reflect the mirror effect in an independent method, they can equally produce a reciprocity effect on the sociological parameters by bringing about group dynamism amongst and between individuals and groups, and a positive state of mind, thus harmonising for a conducive environment.

The growth and development of individuals in a group formation process is replenished with Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters. As discussed, Physiological parameters assimilate the changes and development in sociological and psychological parameters. Similarly, sociological parameters have consequential effects on the psychological and physiological parameters. Furthermore, psychological parameters assimilate both the sociological and physiological development, which further generates well-being from within and to others. Moreover, Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters are integrated with each other and have multi-dimensional reciprocity effects. These PSP parameters are not mutually exclusive. Change through well maintenance in one single parameter can have a mirror effect on other parameters. Nevertheless, simultaneous maintenance of all these three parameters at one single given time may not be possible, but can generate a reciprocity effect on other parameters due to their intertwining nature connections. Therefore, it is essential to maintain an imperative parameter according to the immediate contextual variations, which will spontaneously instigate to maintain the sensitivity of other parameters, furthering to reflect a positive mirror effect towards a responsiveness of the positive reciprocity effects.

In conclusion, Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters maintenance is highly required for all individuals, groups and organisations. Although maintenance of these three parameters may not be significantly applicable at the same time to all individuals and groups, it is found that a single parameter maintenance can equally offer a significant contribution that eventually benefits the well-being of all within an entire organisation. Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters are tightly intertwined with each other and are inseparable; moreover, maintenance of Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters is essential to enhance the growth and development of individuals and groups. Nevertheless, maintenance of these parameters can be focused on a

single parameter to enhance the other two parameters. The mirror effect of one single parameter can have a simultaneous and spontaneous reciprocity effect on the maintenance of the other parameters. Learning to know which parameters need immediate attention for maintenance is important. However, all parameters require maintenance at some point. Although maintenance of a single parameter can have a simultaneous and spontaneous reciprocity effect, it is considered to have a multi-dimensional maintenance of all the Psycho-Socio-Physio (PSP) parameters to bring about the wholesome development and growth in individuals, groups and organisations.

References

- Albarracín, D., Dai, S.A. & White, B. X. (2019). The social creation of action and inaction: From concepts to goals to behaviors. In J. M. Olson (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (pp. 223–271). Elsevier Academic Press.
- Bandura, A. (1999). A social cognitive theory of personality. In L. Pervin & O. John *Hnadbook of personality*. New York, Guilford Publications: 154-196. Psychological review 106(4), 676
- Carmines, E. G., & Zeller, R. A. (1979). *Reliability and validity assessment*. SAGE Publications, Inc., <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412985642>
- Child Trends. (2016). *Child well-being: Constructs to measure child well-being and risk and protective factors that affect the development of young children*. Child Trends. <https://cms.childtrends.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/2016-61ConstructsMeasureChildWellbeing.pdf>
- Correvon, F. (2010). *Children in street situations*. Terre des Hommes. Save the Children. <https://resourcecentre.savethechildren.net/document/children-street-situations>
- Denzin, N.K. (1970). *The research act: A theoretical introduction to sociological methods*. Chicago: Aldine.
- Ellingson, L. (2008). *Engaging Crystallization in Qualitative Research. An Introduction*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Gale, C. & Khatiwada, C. (2016). *Alternative Child Care and Deinstitutionalisation A case study of Nepal*. CELCIS, European Commission, & SOS Children's Villages International. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09751122.2016.11890406>
- Gahungu, L., Simbananiye, L., & Glowacz, F. (2024). Children in Street Situations, Their Determinants, Survival and Strategies: Case of the City of Bujumbura. *European Scientific Journal*, 20(5), 144-169. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2024.v20n5p144>
- Kolb, D.A. (1981). Learning styles and disciplinary differences, in: A.W. Chickering (Ed.) *The Modern American College* (pp. 232–255). San Francisco, LA: Jossey-Bass]
- Lewis, A. (2019). Examining the concept of well-being and early childhood: Adopting multi-disciplinary perspectives. *Journal of Early Childhood Research*, 17(4), 294-308. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1476718X19860553>
- OECD (2020), *Early Learning and Child Well-being: A Study of Five-year-Olds in England, Estonia, and the United States*. OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/3990407f-en>.

- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2013). *School leadership en-route to “grand leap”*: Case studies from Nepal and Finland. Retrieved from <http://tampub.uta.fi/handle/10024/94461>
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2015a). How Does Maintenance of Psycho-Socio-Physio Parameters Enrich Educational Leaders? *The Journal of Educational Thought (JET) / Revue de La Pensée Éducative*, 48(3), 239–254.
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2016). Why do educational leaders need maintenance? *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 12(1), 1–6.
- Rajbhandari, M. M. S. (2025). Artificial Intelligence (AI) Shaping Organizational Culture and Climate over the Human Intelligent Minds (HIM): A Commentary. *SXC Journal*, 2(1), 29–34. <https://doi.org/10.3126/sxcj.v2i1.81663>
- Rajbhandari, M.M.S. & Rajbhandari, S. (2015b), Leadership maintenance: Filling the gap for leadership competences. *Educational Research and Reviews* 10(21), 2777–2788. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5897/ERR2015.2336>
- Saracoğlu, D.S. & Karaoğlu, D. (2016). *Early Childhood Development and Human Capital Formation: The Case of Turkey in Global Perspective*. ERC Working Papers 1605, ERC - Economic Research Center, Middle East Technical University, revised May 2016.
- Schoellman, T. (2016). Early childhood human capital and development. *American Economic Journal: Macroeconomics*, 8, 145-174.
- Social Protection Civil Society Network, Save the Children, & UNICEF Nepal. (2023, April). *Scaling up the child grant, improving the impact on human capital development: Policy brief*. <https://www.unicef.org/nepal/media/18606/file/Policy%20Brief:%20UCG.pdf>. UNICEF.
- UNICEF. (2024). *Study of children in street situations in India*. <https://www.unicef.org/india/media/13451/file/study%20of%20children%20in%20street%20situation%20in%20india.pdf>
- UNICEF. (2015). *why invest in children? investment in children is investment in ‘human capital’*. <https://www.unicef.org/nepal/why-invest-children>

Paper Received February 17, 2026; Accepted April 13, 2026; Published May 2, 2026

